

The Uptake of Higher Level Mathematics: An Analysis of Students' Reasons for Studying Mathematics in its Most Advance Form

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There is a large body of research which highlights the importance of students studying mathematics at an advanced level and many Governments and policy makers worldwide are constantly looking at ways to increase the uptake of advanced mathematics. In Ireland, the Bonus Points Initiative was introduced in 2011 in an attempt to increase the number of Senior Cycle students opting to study higher level mathematics and to improve Irish students' mathematical capabilities. Despite a rise in the number of students studying higher level mathematics at this time very little research has been conducted to determine if it was the initiative, the new curriculum or other factors that led to the surge in uptake. This study investigates Irish students' reasons for participating in higher level mathematics and seeks to determine if the reasons for studying higher level mathematics differs across gender. The findings suggest that the points system currently in place in Ireland is the main driving factor behind students' participation in higher level mathematics while parents are very influential actors in the decision-making process also. Differences in the reasons offered by males and females were also unearthed with higher levels of mathematical self-efficacy among male respondents influencing their decision to study higher level mathematics.

Introduction

There is a large body of growing research which highlights the importance of students studying mathematics at an advanced level (Attridge & Inglis, 2013). For example, Chinnappan et al. (2008) determined that higher-level mathematics facilitates the development of a variety of skills that underpin a scientifically literate workforce. Kennedy, Lyons and Quinn (2014) added that higher-level mathematics courses in high school are critical if we are to produce graduates who are capable and confident in making informed decisions about various real life issues. The literature also highlights the importance of advanced mathematics for developing students' logical thinking and reasoning abilities. For example, in a year-long study of students in the United Kingdom, Attridge and Inglis (2013) recorded differences in the conditional reasoning abilities of advanced mathematics students compared with non-mathematics students. The Irish senior cycle higher level mathematics syllabus places particular emphasis 'on the development of powers of abstraction and generalisation and on the idea of rigorous proof' (DES, 2013, p. 11). With this in mind, many researchers hypothesize that there is a correlation between participation rates in higher level mathematics and participation in other science subjects such as physics (Chinnappan et al., 2008; Kennedy et al., 2014) and chemistry (Donovan & Wheland, 2009). Furthermore, many science, engineering, and technology Level 8-degree courses in Ireland have minimum requirements for attainment in Leaving Certificate higher level mathematics, meaning that without studying mathematics in its most advanced form at upper secondary level many

students are limiting the options available to them at third level and this will have a detrimental effect on the potential supply of graduate recruits for third-level science, technology, engineering, and mathematics (STEM) courses (EGFSN, 2008). This is particularly important in Ireland where the Government have set a goal that the country will become a leader in Europe with regards to developing and deploying STEM talent by 2026 (DES, 2017).

Despite the importance of higher-level mathematics many countries worldwide have reported low numbers of students opting to study mathematics in its most advanced form. For example, in Australia, Goodrum, Druhan and Abbs (2012) found that all high school science subjects, mathematics included, were experiencing dramatic declines. In addition to this, in the UK participation in higher level mathematics, that is mathematics post-GCSE level (age 16), has been a cause of concern for many years. According to Noyes (2013) only 10-15% of 16-year-old students choose to continue their study of mathematics and he reported that this figure is low when compared with other developed countries. Similar problems were also reported in the USA and India (National Commission on Mathematics and Science Teaching, 2000; Garg & Gupta, 2003). In Ireland, while the uptake of mathematics at Senior Cycle is not a cause for concern, due in no small part to the fact that mathematics acts as a gatekeeper to higher education, for many years there has been concern around the low numbers of students opting to study higher level mathematics. For example, in 2011 15.8% of Irish students opted to study higher-level mathematics for their Leaving Certificate compared with 63.7% for English; 73.4% for Physics; 81.7% for Chemistry; 74.7% for Biology and 32.2% for Irish. In order to address this problem, and to improve the standard of mathematics among second level graduates, the Irish government introduced the Bonus Points initiative. This initiative rewarded students with 25 additional CAO points¹ if they achieved 40% or higher in their Leaving Certificate mathematics exam. This initiative was introduced in 2012 and the proportion of students studying higher level mathematics jumped from 15.8% in 2011 to 22.8% in 2012 and there has been a steady increase year on year ever since, with 32.9% of students sitting the higher level mathematics exam in 2019. This suggests that the Bonus Points Initiative has been successful in achieving one of its aims, to increase the proportion of students studying higher level mathematics. However, in the same year that the Bonus Points Initiative was introduced a new mathematics curriculum, known locally as Project Maths, which placed a much stronger emphasis on teaching mathematics for understanding and through the use of real life applications was also introduced so this too may have contributed to the recent surge in the

¹ Students are awarded points based on the result they obtain in each subject in the Leaving Certificate and the number of points awarded varies depending on whether the subject is studied at higher or ordinary level. A student who achieves the top grade (H1 = 100% - 90%) at higher level is awarded 100 while the same score at ordinary level is awarded 56 points (see <http://www2.cao.ie/downloads/documents/CommonPointsGradingSystem.pdf>). The total number of points a student accumulates across six subjects dictates the third level college courses for which they are eligible.

uptake of higher level mathematics. This study seeks to determine which of these factors, if any, play a role in students' decision to pursue higher level mathematics.

In addition to this, in recent years, elsewhere around the globe, many researchers have invested a lot of time and effort into identifying possible reasons why students do not continue to study mathematics in upper secondary school or why they do not choose to study mathematics in its most advanced form. A range of different reasons have been identified including low levels of perceived competence in mathematics among students (Nagy et al., 2010); students' dissatisfaction with mathematics (Hine, 2019); perceived level of difficulty of the subject (Hine, 2019) and the excessive amount of time that the subject requires in order to succeed (Chen & Liu, 2009). However, very little research has been conducted internationally or in Ireland to determine the reasons behind students' decision to pursue higher level mathematics. Uncovering these reasons may help policy makers and educators to develop more strategies that will help to improve uptake of higher level mathematics, retention in higher level mathematics and performance in the subject.

Research Questions

In order to address the aforementioned gaps in the literature this study sought to determine Irish students' reasons for opting to study higher level mathematics. As a result, the research questions underpinning this study are:

1. What are the most influential factors in students' decision to pursue higher level mathematics in Ireland?
2. Do the reasons for studying higher level mathematics differ across gender, and if so, in what way?

Methodology

Research Design and Instrument

To address these research questions the authors chose to employ a survey research design. They utilised a survey which had been designed and validated for use in Queensland, Australia, another jurisdiction where incentives are in place for the uptake of advanced mathematics. Two versions of this survey were developed one for those who chose to study higher level and one for those who chose to study mathematics at ordinary level. For this paper, the authors will solely focus on the survey designed for students studying higher level.

The survey yielded both qualitative and quantitative data. Quantitative data was collected in Section A and Section B of the survey. In Section A student demographics were recorded while in Section B students were provided with eighteen potential reasons for opting to study higher level mathematics and asked to state, on a five-point Likert scale², if they agreed or disagreed that each of the reasons played a significant role in their decision. Qualitative data was collected in Section C of the survey when three open ended questions were posed to students. First students were asked to outline any other reasons that contributed to their decision

² The Likert Scale used was as follows: 1 = Strongly Agree; 2 = Agree; 3 = Neither Agree nor Disagree; 4 = Disagree; 5 = Strongly Disagree.

to study higher level mathematics and then they were asked of all the reasons listed, including any they provided themselves, which did they consider the most influential reason. Finally, students were then asked to describe how they came to the decision to study higher level mathematics and when they made this decision.

Sample

In total the authors sought to survey 2000 second level students and in order to achieve this number 12 schools were selected using convenience sampling. Five vocational schools and seven secondary schools were invited to participate, a school breakdown that aligned with the national breakdown. However, two schools withdrew and the final sample consisted of three vocational schools and seven secondary schools. In total 1706 senior cycle students responded to the survey and 53.4% ($n = 911$) of the sample were studying higher level mathematics at the time the survey was conducted. It is the responses of these 911 students that will be analysed and discussed in this paper. Table 1 outlines the gender and year group of the sample. 48.3% of the sample were male and 50.7% were female. 54.3% of the sample were in 5th year while the remaining 45.7% were in sixth year.

Table 1

	5 th Year	6 th Year
Male	236	204
Female	254	208
Other/Prefer Not to Say	5	4

Results

The first research question sought to determine the reasons behind students' decision to study higher-level mathematics and to determine if it was in fact bonus points that led to the recent surge in the uptake of higher level mathematics in Ireland. Figure 1 shows students' level of agreement with the 18 reasons for studying higher level mathematics. It shows that the three reasons which had strongest levels of agreement were *I wanted to get bonus points* (91.2% of students agreed or strongly agreed with this statement); *I will get good CAO points from it* (80.3% of students agreed or strongly agreed with this statement) and *my parents suggested I do it* (73.4% of students agreed or strongly agreed with this statement). This shows that CAO points, and in particular the provision of bonus points, is one of the real driving factors in the uptake of higher level mathematics while parents are the most significant actors influencing a student's decision to study higher level mathematics.

Students were also asked to outline what they believed to be the most influential factor out of all of those listed. The results are presented in Figure 2. In total 893 students offered a response to this question and almost half of these students, 46.2% ($n = 413$) indicated that of all the possible reasons listed bonus points was considered the most influential factor in their decision. A further 7.2% ($n = 64$) stated that the CAO points on offer was the determining factor. This indicates that the majority of students were extrinsically motivated to study higher level mathematics and the main reason for over half of the students in this study opting for

Figure 1
Students' level of agreement with the different reasons for studying higher level mathematics

higher level mathematics was as a result of the points system in place in Ireland. On the other hand, only 4.4% of respondents stated that they chose higher level mathematics because they found it interesting; 5.9% stated that they chose higher level because they are good at mathematics while a mere 0.7% of respondents said they opted for higher level mathematics because the skills developed will help them in their everyday life. In addition to this, a further 8.5% of students gave an answer of “other” or cited more than one reason when asked to outline the most influential factor in their decision. Students who gave such answers were asked to elaborate and analysis of this qualitative data showed that of the 76 students in this category, 58 were there because they offered more than one factor, and 93.1% ($n = 54$) of these responses included a reference to bonus points ($n = 35$) and CAO points ($n = 19$).

Figure 2

Predominant reason for studying higher level mathematics as reported by students

The authors also wished to investigate if the reasons for studying higher level mathematics differed across gender. Of the 18 reasons outlined in the questionnaire, significant differences between the levels of agreement offered by males and females were recorded in nine of the statements. The most notable differences were recorded for the statements “*I need higher level mathematics for my university course*” and “*I think I will get good marks*”. The average male score for “*I need higher level mathematics for my university course*” was 2.50 (s.d. = 1.27) while the median score among this cohort was 2. The corresponding mean among female students was 2.94 (s.d. = 1.27) while the median was 3. As the data for this response was not normally distributed and the data was ordinal a Mann Whitney U test was carried out to determine if the differences recorded were statistically significant. This test showed that the male score was significantly lower than the female score ($U = 80627, p < 0.001$), meaning that male students were more likely to agree with this statement. For the second statement, “*I think I will get good marks*” the mean score for males was 2.42 (s.d. = 0.76; median = 2) while the mean score among females was 2.73 (s.d. = 0.86; median = 3). In this instance the responses were normally distributed but because the dependent variable was ordinal a t -test was not appropriate and so a Mann Whitney U test was again conducted to determine if the differences recorded were statistically significant. This test showed that again the differences recorded were statistically significant ($U = 80860.5, p < 0.001$). This indicates that males were more likely to agree with this statement than their

female counterparts. Another interesting finding, when results were compared across gender, was that for all the reasons relating to self-efficacy (e.g. *I study higher level mathematics because I am good at maths* or *I study higher level mathematics because maths is my best subject*) males recorded a significantly lower average score than females, thus suggesting that reasons of this nature are more likely to influence a male's decision to study higher level mathematics compared to females. This indicates that males' self-belief in relation to mathematical performance is higher than females and this played a role in their choice to pursue higher level mathematics.

Conclusion

The first research question sought to determine the influential factors in students' decision to pursue higher level mathematics. The findings have shown the true extent of the influence of the bonus points initiative on students' decision to study mathematics in its most advanced form. While recent studies have suggested that this was the case (Authors, 2019), this is the first study that has definitively shown the influence of this initiative and the authors hypothesise that without this initiative and the CAO points system in Ireland it is highly likely that the proportion of students studying higher level mathematics would be drastically lower. With the points system as the driving force behind students' decision-making process it is little wonder that many teachers believe that students are pursuing higher level mathematics despite struggling with the content (O'Meara et al., 2020). This presents many challenges to students and teachers alike and so the authors recommend that policy makers look at other initiatives to improve students' attitudes towards mathematics in lower secondary school in the hope that intrinsic reasons such as liking mathematics or having a deep-rooted interest in the subject will play a more influential role in students' decision to study higher level mathematics in the future.

This research study also sought to determine if gender played a role in students' reasoning for studying higher level mathematics. The results showed that males were more likely to suggest that their perceived capability in mathematics and their liking of the subject was a reason behind their decision to study higher level mathematics compared to females. While research has pointed to differences in attitudes towards mathematics across gender (Frenzel, Pekrun & Goetz, 2007) for many years this study shows that these differences are contributing to students' decision to study higher level mathematics and so it is important, going forward, that efforts are made to improve female students' attitudes towards mathematics in Ireland in the hope that this will have a knock on effect on female students' opting to study higher level mathematics.

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